

AN ANALYTICAL COMPARISON OF MACHINE LEARNING MODELS FOR CREDIT CARD ANOMALY DETECTION

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ABSTRACT

In recent times, a significant increase in the use of credit cards have led to a surge in fraudulent activity. It is because of the extensive use of credit cards that the development of online businesses and the convenience of the electronic payment system have both increased. The incorporation of machine learning (ML) techniques is being implemented on larger scales to detect and prevent fraud. When it comes to the analysis of user data, machine learning algorithms are a critical component. In this research, numerous ML-based algorithms for credit card anomaly detection are presented. Some examples of these approaches are the Decision Tree, Random Forest, XGBoost and MLP. The research utilized European card benchmark datasets to carry out the extensive empirical analysis that is performed to detect anomalies in the data. Additionally, the research has also adopted balancing data techniques in order to minimize the number of false negatives. The proposed system can be deployed robustly for the real-world applications banking industries.

Keywords: Machine Learning (ML), XGBoost, Anomaly Detection, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Random Forest (RF)

Cite this Article: Kaushik Sathupadi, Sandesh Achar, An Analytical Comparison of Machine Learning Models for Credit Card Anomaly Detection, International Journal of Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning (IJAIML), 3(2), 2024, pp. 173-181.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJAIML/VOLUME_3_ISSUE_2/IJAIML_03_02_013.pdf

1. INTRODUCTION

Credit card fraud is a form of identity theft in which an individual other than the owner utilizes a credit card or account number to conduct an unauthorized transaction [1]. Whereas, a credit card that has been theft, forgotten, or forged may lead to fraud. Card-not-present fraud, which involves the fraudulent active use of the person's credit card information in e-commerce purchases [2].

Credit cards are now widely used for conducting routine financial transactions, such as commercial transactions and real-time services [3]. Electronic devices that are connected to the Internet, including cell phones, tablets, and PCs, are utilised by consumers to make purchases. Nevertheless, the widespread use of electronic banking and a variety of online payment systems has led to a rise in the risk of committing fraud, which can result in substantial financial losses of billions of dollars yearly [4].

According to European Central Bank seventh report on card fraud in 2021, the total amount of fraud attempts via cards made within SEPA and collected globally numbered to €1.87 billion in 2019 [5]. Whereas, for cards used in the Europe only, the total amount of these card transactions valued to €1.03 billion. The Malaysian banking sector recorded an overall loss of RM 51.3 million in forged credit card transactions in 2016, which is a significant loss [6]. Additionally, the Malaysian government expressed unease regarding the 12.8% of credit cardholders in

Malaysia that was having difficulty meeting the minimum balance payment. Financial organisations must resolve numerous credit card-related concerns, such as (i) the issue of card owners disregarding refunds, which results in default payments, and (ii) the presence of unauthorised third parties contributing to fraud. The resolution of this issue can be substantially facilitated by the implementation of an automated anomaly detection system.

In general, credit card datasets having key categories, such as default payments and fraud, which are routinely underestimated. On the other hand, learning algorithms can identify and learning trends from these types of data when they have an adequate number of records. However, the work steps increasingly complex when the sample size in these classes are inadequate, as it complicates the accurate definition and generalization of their decision limits using conventional learning techniques. [7].

A variety of research projects have examined machine learning algorithms to address the challenges of identifying fraud and anomalies in credit card data. Most algorithms involve decision trees, SVM, random forest, neural networks, and logistic regression [8-9]. Furthermore, the dataset's complex and dynamic nature often gives rise to a reduced accuracy rate for the detection of anomalies in credit card transactions (CCT).

Most current methods predict anomalies by employing a single classifier, which has not been effective in detecting anomalies in CCT with greater accuracy.

In this research, the main goal is to recognize anomalies in credit cards with the assistance of machine learning (ML) algorithms. The main contributions of this paper are as follows.

- We used feature selection approach to minimize the overhead of all descriptors
- Data balancing strategies are adopted to handle imbalance issues.
- We performed a comparative analysis by incorporating multiple machine learning algorithms to test the performance of proposed approach on benchmark datasets.

The remaining parts are organized as follows: Section II presents the existing studies on credit card anomaly detection techniques. In Section III, we discussed the method and framework for anomaly detection. Section IV provides the comparative analysis on benchmark datasets. Finally, in Section V, conclusions and research directions are presented.

II. RELATED WORK

The dataset's complex and dynamic nature frequently leads to a decreasing accuracy rate for the detection of anomalies in credit card transactions. Therefore, single-supervised machine learning classifiers often face challenges in capturing the intricate characteristics that are inherent in credit card operations. Currently, most methods anticipate anomalies by utilizing a single classifier, which has not been more effective at recognizing anomalies in credit card transactions with higher precision.

The conventional algorithms including logistic regression, C4,5, and random forest are implemented. The relationship between the dependent binary variable and the independent variable is described and analyzed by logistic regression. Whereas the C4.5 is commonly employed as DT classifiers in data mining to generate decisions based on a variety of data sets [10].

Vynokurova et al. [11] have devised a hybrid approach to identifying instances of credit card fraud that incorporates random forest and isolation for EST. This method is employed to identify transactions that are unusual. The framework proposed by the researcher is based on two main subsystems. One of them is concerned about the identification of anomalies that relies on unsupervised learning.

The second notion encompasses the anomalies class. For example, research in [12] have created a model that is based on backpropagation and the ANN to identify instances of credit card fraud. The dataset of consumers is acquired, which comprises their name, purchase ID, and time. The author utilised 80% of the data for training, while 20% was for testing and validation. A significant outcome was obtained by the proposed model in the recognition of forged events in real-time data.

Data mining approaches, including the random forest, DT, and MLP are commonly used to identify patterns from previous transactions. Frequently, these algorithms employ two distinct datasets to evaluate their performance.

In this context, Rtayli et al. [13] have developed a hybrid approach that employs the random forest classifier and SVM to analyze credit card fraud risk (CCR) in high-dimensional data. The selection of features of fraudulent transactions in the large imbalanced dataset served as a basis for the concept. It is challenging to detect the fraud transactions due to the lack of them. In order to assess the model, the author used assessment indicators that encompass the area under the curve, recall, and accuracy.

KNN is a supervised learning method that is useful in the classification and execution of regression analyses on issues [14]. It is an effective approach to supervised learning. The KNN fraud detection method entails two predicts: the relationship of the transaction and the distance between the transaction's occurrence in the data, respectively. It is feasible to identify forged information during transaction time using the KNN technique. Awoyemi et al. [15] used KNN approach to identify a similar pattern in the cardholder's previous transactions. The performance of KNN has been demonstrated to be efficient in all metrics that have been employed, as it found difficult to identify any false positives during the classification process. Table 1 shows the key findings and focus of the study in the existing research.

Table 1 Key findings and Focus of the study

Author(s)	Approach	Key Findings	Relevance to Fraud Detection
Vynokurova et al., [11]	Hybrid approach combining RF and Isolation Forest	Identified unusual transactions using a hybrid of RF and Isolation Forest for anomaly detection.	Proposes an effective hybrid approach for anomaly detection in credit card fraud by utilizing two systems.
Dubey et al. [12]	Backpropagation and (ANN)	Achieved significant accuracy in real-time fraud detection using ANN and backpropagation techniques.	Shows effectiveness of ANN in detecting forged transactions with high real-time accuracy.
Rtayli et al., [13]	Hybrid approach using Random Forest and SVM for High-Dimensional Data	Focused on feature selection for large imbalanced datasets, utilizing AUC, recall, and accuracy metrics.	Demonstrated the capability of Random Forest and SVM in handling high-dimensional, imbalanced fraud data.
Awoyemi et al., [15]	K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)	Demonstrated high performance in fraud detection, particularly in avoiding false positives.	KNN was effective in identifying fraudulent patterns based on transaction distances and similarities.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

The proposed approach utilizes numerous ML classifiers to recognize fraudulent credit card transactions based on different evaluation parameters such as, accuracy, precision, recall and F-score. Initially, data is processed to handle missing or null values. Then, we extracted polynomial features of degree 2 to capture interactions between variables. Then, feature selection approach is adopted to select optimal features. Finally, multiple classifiers are applied to test the performance of the system. Fig. 1 shows the workflow and layout of the proposed system.

Fig. 1 The architectural layout of the proposed HMR framework.

A. Pre-processing

In this study, we acquired benchmark dataset from a publicly available repository Kaggle [16]. The database incorporates both authentic and counterfeit credit card transactions. In the initial phase we performed exploratory data analysis to get filtered data without noise. The function facilitating in recognizing null and missing values that are filtered during the denoising process. Figure 2 shows the correlation heatmap of benchmark dataset.

Fig. 2 The correlation heatmap of Kaggle dataset

B. Data Balancing

We initiate a classification task on an unbalanced dataset. In other words, it can be a substantial challenge to train a model using an unbalanced dataset. As a result, we utilize a variety of sampling techniques, such as SMOTE, and near-miss sampling [17].

C. Feature Extraction

To extract the main descriptors from the processed data. We utilized polynomial features. These features construct a new feature matrix that comprises all polynomial a mixture of the features with a degree that is less than or equal to the designated degree. The representation of a features is depicted in figure 3.

Fig. 3 The representation of selected features

D. Feature Selection

We use SMOTE and near-sampling data for feature selection with random forest algorithm. All the features are selected based on their significance by selecting threshold ‘mean’ to get optimal features. The random forest algorithm is an intriguing option for this project due to its features. It is a collection of numerous weak classifiers, each of which is built using a distinct subset of variables and objects [18].

Additionally, the significance of the attribute is determined simply by the trees that employ the attribute in question. Consequently, the signal for attributes that contribute to a small number of trees remains distinct. Figure 4 shows the 15 optimal features selected by the random forest.

Fig. 4 The 15 optimal features directed by random forest

Algorithm 1 Feature selection using Random Forest

Step	Action	Keywords/Variables
1	Generate feature names	feature_names, num_features
2	Convert data to DataFrame	X_train_df
3	Initialize Random Forest model	rf_model, n_estimators, random_state
4	Train model	X_train_selected, y_train_smote
5	Extract feature importances	importances
6	Create feature importance table	feature_importance_df
7	Sort features by importance	sorted_importance_df
8	Visualize top features	top_n_features, bar_plot

IV. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

A. Dataset Description

This research made use of the database that is dedicated to the detection of fraudulent credit card activity. The dataset involve European cardholders carried out transactions [19]. A total of 31 numerical attributes are included in the dataset. The total number of transactions in the database is 284,807 out of these, 492 were deemed to be fraudulent, while the remaining transactions were deemed to be valid. Figure 5 shows the class distribution over fraud and non-fraud transactions.

Fig. 5 Class distribution over 0 and 1 transactions

B. Experimental Analysis

In this phase, we incorporated multiple machine learning algorithms. These algorithms involve decision trees, random forest, multilayer perceptron [20], and XGBoost [21]. In addition, data mining, classification, statistical learning, and association analysis are all possible applications of these techniques.

1. Metrics for all Models

A visualization of a classification framework is a confusion evaluation metric that illustrates how well the model is expected to fit the results that were initially connected with the earliest ones. It is common practice to store the anticipated outcomes in a variable, which is subsequently transformed into an association table. The representation of the confusion metrics of machine learning algorithms are depicted in Figure 5.

Fig. 6 Confusion metrics of ML algorithms

We incorporated four main algorithms on our benchmark dataset, and we have found that random forest and XGBoost achieves better results score over decision trees, and MLP classifiers. Both random forest and XGBoost minimizes false positives and false negatives more effectively than other models. On the other hand, decision high accuracy and low f-measure score indicates it struggles to accurately classify fraudulent activities. The results based on decision trees suggest that decision trees are imbalanced in handling both classes.

Table 1 ML Algorithms Comparison of ML Algorithms

ML Algorithms	Accuracy	F-measure
Decision Trees	99.70%	47.3%
Random Forest	99.94%	83.3%
MLP	99.92%	76.9%
XGBoost	99.99%	81.9%

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a comparative analysis for credit card anomaly detection. The preprocessing and data balancing techniques are applied to handle the missing values and any irrelevant data. In addition, we introduce random forest algorithm as a feature selection approach to select the optimal features from the given data. Furthermore, multiple classifiers are applied to test the performance of proposed system on the benchmark datasets. The results have shown that XGBoost and random forest have performed better when compared with other state-of-the-art algorithms.

The only limitation of this system is that the approach does not have a balanced dataset for training purposes, and inadequacy of the datasets.

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Citation: Kaushik Sathupadi, Sandesh Achar, An Analytical Comparison of Machine Learning Models for Credit Card Anomaly Detection, *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning (IJAIML)*, 3(2), 2024, pp. 173-181

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